

REMOVING BACKWARD COUNTRIES FROM BACKWARD

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola qoloq mamlakatalarning bugungi muammosi, qanday vaziyatlarga to'qnash kelishayotganliklari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek, iqtisodiy qoloqlikka duch kelayotganliklarining sababalari nimadan iborat ekanligi hamda ularga bir nechta yechim ko'rsatamiz.

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The economic backwardness of the so-called underdeveloped countries is not just a matter of their lagging behind developed countries. It consists primarily in the international division of labor, which is arranged exclusively in the interests of the imperialist countries.

As a result, backward countries under the worldwide domination of imperialism are forever doomed to backwardness. The political independence and possession of the national State apparatus, which most underdeveloped countries acquired during decolonization, provided the ruling classes in these countries with great opportunities for exchange with the imperialist Powers in the distribution of national surplus value. But this new political form did not put an end to their basic subordination to Western capital and economic dependence on it. Western capital has closed all paths to development to underdeveloped countries.

Why are these countries backward?

1. Capital Scarcity: Capital is critical to economic growth, but this is precisely what underdeveloped countries lack.
2. Lack of Entrepreneurial and Managerial Talent: Lack of this talent is the reason why profitable investment opportunities are not available. Consequently, such countries remain economically backward.
3. Lack of qualified personnel and technical know-how: Building these elements of a productive force takes a long time and foreign specialists are very expensive. Consequently, underdeveloped countries remain underdeveloped.
4. Limited Market Size: People's purchasing power is very low due to their notorious poverty. Consequently, manufacturing enterprises experience difficulties in selling goods. Only an expanding market can provide a fertile field for profitable investment and lead to the country's economic development.

5. Weak Infrastructure: Lacking countries lack adequate and efficient means of transport and communication, a well-organized and developed banking system, and adequate opportunities for technical education.

6. Social and institutional structure:

The social customs and attitudes of people in backward countries are a serious obstacle to economic progress. Conservatism, superstition, lack of ambition, excessive respect for customs and status hinder economic progress. The economic backwardness in India is due in no small part to the joint family system, the caste system, the special laws of inheritance, and the otherworldly attitudes of the people.

7. Foreign rule:

Most of these countries were under foreign rule, which suppressed them. Foreign rulers cannot be expected to show any genuine interest in the economic recovery of the people. The economic backwardness of India may be largely due to the policies pursued by its British rulers.

8. population growth:

Explosive population growth in underdeveloped countries is undoubtedly slowing down their economic growth. Any falsified development is swallowed up by the growing influx of population. The fruits of development are hardly enough to feed a flood of babies.

9. the predominance of agriculture:

The main part of the population is engaged in agriculture, which is carried out in a primitive way. Naturally, the national income remains low. Economic development cannot be secured in the absence of rapid industrialization.

What problems are you currently facing?:

- Per capita income in the country is very low compared to developing economies.
- The population will be so high that it will also lead to the unavailability of resources for residents.
- Unemployment prevails to a greater extent due to lack of resources, and people are more likely to be underemployed.
- The country's wealth is low, which ultimately leads to a decrease in their capital.
- Unfair distribution of wealth and income
- Predominance of agriculture
- Illiteracy prevails
- Lack of technological progress

- Low standard of living
- High fertility and mortality rates.
- Poor medical care.

The total number of backward countries is 48, and 33 of them are located on the African continent. Africa is a huge treasure that has preserved various valuable natural resources on its land. The widespread distribution of igneous rocks in Africa has caused a large number of ore minerals to be found. Africa ranks first in the world in diamond mining. Ancient crystal rocks are rich in iron ore, chromium, copper, zinc, tin, uranium ore, gold and precious stones. The famous "copper region" is located in the border zone of Zambia and the Democratic Republic of the Congo. In the places of accumulation of batik, sedimentary rocks of the mainland, fossil fuels, oil, natural gas, manganese ores, salts, phosphorites are common.

According to statistics from South Africa Tourism and Migration Survey, in August 2017, almost 3.5 million travelers passed through the country's access ports.[3] the five foreign countries most visited by tourists to South Africa are the United States, Great Britain, Germany, the Netherlands and France.

But nevertheless Africa is the abode of backward countries, why?

Backwardness cannot be explained by one or two factors. This is a multidimensional phenomenon. It is undeniable that people are economically and educationally backward. In the first place, the level of literacy is very low, which means that most people do not know their problems. Who is different from the state, and what is their goal? The leader who wants to develop the state should first of all pay attention to the direction of Education. The reason is the pillar of the state. Citizens with political , economic, social, cultural knowledge will be able to see the problem shortcomings of dacvlat. In Case b, the main

objective that the person in charge of the state does not focus on it is another. Or rather is the management of unconscious citizens.

Backwardness is a cumulative phenomenon that increases in the long term. The only way to overcome backwardness in education is to educate people through education. The government must find the maximum budgetary resources for the development of Education.

It is necessary to give strength to people in the field of education by allocating funds for Education, people, as soon as they become educated, will be able to overcome ignorance, prejudice, leading social vices. Education brings people Intelligence, rationality. The real empowerment of people lies in education.

In a second, issue does not need charity to poor countries. They need justice. And it is not difficult to ensure justice. We can write off the excess debts of poor countries, freeing them from spending their money on development instead of paying interest on old loans. we can close secret jurisdictions and impose fines on bankers and accountants who contribute to the illegal outflow of capital, and we can introduce a global minimum corporate income tax to eliminate incentives for corporations to secretly transfer their money around the world. If international organizations had taken this seriously and considered the human factor as the main factor, now they would have served to develop territories on the balcony, and not to force the territories from behind. No one will do the same without interest.

List of used literature:

1. Эрнест Жермен. Индустриализация отсталых стран
2. <https://www.economicdiscussion.net/wp-content/themes/canvas-child/createimage.php?author=Tushar%20Seth&height=20&width=132>

